

THE IMPORTANCE OF TROPONIN AND MOLECULAR-GENETIC FACTORS IN EARLY DETECTION OF CARDIOTOXIC COMPLICATIONS IN THE BACKGROUND OF ANTHRACYCLINE CHEMOTHERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH ACUTE LEUKEMIA

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ABSTRACT

Cardiotoxic complications associated with anthracycline chemotherapy are an important clinical problem that limits the effectiveness of treatment and long-term prognosis in patients with acute leukemia. Detection of cardiotoxicity at an early, subclinical stage is of great clinical importance, and the interaction of biochemical markers of heart damage and molecular-genetic factors plays an important role in this process. Genetic determinants may determine individual myocardial sensitivity to anthracyclines and modify the risk of developing cardiotoxic complications.

Relevance. Cardiotoxic complications associated with anthracycline chemotherapy are an important clinical problem that limits the effectiveness of treatment and long-term prognosis in patients with acute leukemia. Detection of cardiotoxicity at an early, subclinical stage is of great clinical importance, and the interaction of biochemical markers of heart damage and molecular-genetic factors plays an important role in this process. Genetic determinants may determine individual myocardial sensitivity to anthracyclines and modify the risk of developing cardiotoxic complications.

Objective: To assess the combined role of troponin parameters and molecular genetic factors in the early detection of cardiotoxic complications developing against the background of anthracycline chemotherapy in patients with acute leukemia.

Materials and methods. A total of 97 patients with acute leukemia were included in the study, of which 57 had acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) and 40 had acute myeloblastic leukemia (AML). All patients were treated according to standard chemotherapy regimens including anthracyclines. Clinical

observation, echocardiography, and determination of blood troponin levels were performed to assess cardiotoxic complications. In addition, two gene polymorphisms associated with endothelial function and oxidative stress were analyzed using molecular genetic methods.

Results. During the follow-up period, an increase in troponin levels was detected in some patients before clinical or echocardiographic changes. At the same time, a correlation was observed between the dynamics of troponin indicators and the development of cardiotoxic complications in carriers of certain genetic variants. The results obtained indicate the joint participation of molecular-genetic factors and biochemical markers in the formation of cardiotoxicity.

Conclusion. Troponin is a sensitive biomarker for the early detection of anthracycline-induced cardiotoxic complications. Its use in combination with molecular-genetic factors allows for individual assessment of cardiovascular risk in patients with acute leukemia, optimization of monitoring and prevention strategies